

Some Remarks on Fuzzy N-Normed Spaces

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Abstract: It is shown that every fuzzy n -normed space naturally induces a locally convex topology, and that every finite dimensional fuzzy n -normed space is complete.

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§1. Introduction

A Smarandache space is such a space that a straight line passing through a point p may turn an angle $\theta_p \geq 0$. If $\theta_p > 0$, then p is called a non-Euclidean. Otherwise, we call it an Euclidean point. In this paper, normed spaces are considered to be Euclidean, i.e., every point is Euclidean. In [7], S. Gähler introduced n -norms on a linear space. A detailed theory of n -normed linear space can be found in [8], [10], [12]-[13]. In [8], H. Gunawan and M. Mashadi gave a simple way to derive an $(n-1)$ -norm from the n -norm in such a way that the convergence and completeness in the n -norm is related to those in the derived $(n-1)$ -norm. A detailed theory of fuzzy normed linear space can be found in [1], [3]-[6], [9], [11] and [15]. In [14], A. Narayanan and S. Vijayabalaji have extend n -normed linear space to fuzzy n -normed linear space. In section 2, we quote some basic definitions, and we show that a fuzzy n -norm is closely related to an ascending system of n -seminorms. In Section 3, we introduce a locally convex topology in a fuzzy n -normed space, and in Section 4 we consider finite dimensional fuzzy n -normed linear spaces.

§2. Fuzzy n -norms and ascending families of n -seminorms

Let n be a positive integer, and let X be a real vector space of dimension at least n . We recall the definitions of an n -seminorm and a fuzzy n -norm [14].

Definition 2.1 A function $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \mapsto \|x_1, \dots, x_n\|$ from X^n to $[0, \infty)$ is called an n -seminorm on X if it has the following four properties:

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- (S1) $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\| = 0$ if x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are linearly dependent;
 (S2) $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|$ is invariant under any permutation of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ;
 (S3) $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, cx_n\| = |c| \|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n\|$ for any real c ;
 (S4) $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y + z\| \leq \|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y\| + \|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, z\|$.

An n -seminorm is called a n -norm if $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\| > 0$ whenever x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are linearly independent.

Definition 2.2 A fuzzy subset N of $X^n \times \mathbb{R}$ is called a fuzzy n -norm on X if and only if:

- (F1) For all $t \leq 0$, $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = 0$;
 (F2) For all $t > 0$, $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = 1$ if and only if x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are linearly dependent;
 (F3) $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t)$ is invariant under any permutation of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ;
 (F4) For all $t > 0$ and $c \in \mathbb{R}$, $c \neq 0$,

$$N(x_1, x_2, \dots, cx_n, t) = N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, \frac{t}{|c|});$$

- (F5) For all $s, t \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y + z, s + t) \geq \min \{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y, s), N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, z, t)\}.$$

- (F6) $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t)$ is a non-decreasing function of $t \in \mathbb{R}$ and

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = 1.$$

The following two theorems clarify the relationship between definitions 2.1 and 2.2.

Theorem 2.1 Let N be a fuzzy n -norm on X . As in [14] define for $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$

$$(2.1) \quad \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha := \inf \{t : N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) \geq \alpha\}.$$

Then the following statements hold.

- (A1) For every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, $\|\bullet, \bullet, \dots, \bullet\|_\alpha$ is an n -seminorm on X ;
 (A2) If $0 < \alpha < \beta < 1$ and $x_1, \dots, x_n \in X$ then

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha \leq \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\beta;$$

- (A3) If $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ are linearly independent then

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha = \infty.$$

Proof (A1) and (A2) are shown in Theorem 3.4 in [14]. Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ be linearly independent, and $t > 0$ be given. We set $\beta := N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t)$. It follows from (F2) that $\beta \in [0, 1)$. Then (F6) shows that, for $\alpha \in (\beta, 1)$,

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha \geq t.$$

This proves (A3). □

We now prove a converse of Theorem 2.2.

Theorem 2.2 *Suppose we are given a family $\|\bullet, \bullet, \dots, \bullet\|_\alpha$, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, of n -seminorms on X with properties (A2) and (A3). We define*

$$(2.2) \quad N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) := \inf\{\alpha \in (0, 1) : \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha \geq t\}.$$

where the infimum of the empty set is understood as 1. Then N is a fuzzy n -norm on X .

Proof (F1) holds because the values of an n -seminorm are nonnegative.

(F2): Let $t > 0$. If x_1, \dots, x_n are linearly dependent then $N(x_1, \dots, x_n, t) = 1$ follows from property (S1) of an n -seminorm. If x_1, \dots, x_n are linearly independent then $N(x_1, \dots, x_n, t) < 1$ follows from (A3).

(F3) is a consequence of property (S2) of an n -seminorm.

(F4) is a consequence of property (S3) of an n -seminorm.

(F5): Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ satisfy

$$(2.3) \quad \alpha < \min\{N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y, s), N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, z, s)\}.$$

It follows that $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y\|_\alpha < s$ and $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, z\|_\alpha < t$. Then (S4) gives

$$\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y + z\|_\alpha < s + t.$$

Using (A2) we find $N(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y + z, s + t) \geq \alpha$ and, since α is arbitrary in (2.3), (F5) follows.

(F6): Definition 2.2 shows that N is non-decreasing in t . Moreover, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N(x_1, \dots, x_n, t) = 1$ because seminorms have finite values. □

It is easy to see that Theorems 2.1 and 2.2 establish a one-to-one correspondence between fuzzy n -norms with the additional property that the function $t \mapsto N(x_1, \dots, x_n, t)$ is left-continuous for all x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n and families of n -seminorms with properties (A2), (A3) and the additional property that $\alpha \mapsto \|x_1, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha$ is left-continuous for all x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n .

Example 2.3(Example 3.3 in [14]). Let $\|\bullet, \bullet, \dots, \bullet\|$ be a n -norm on X . Then define $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = 0$ if $t \leq 0$ and, for $t > 0$,

$$N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = \frac{t}{t + \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|}.$$

Then the seminorms (2.1) are given by

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha = \frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha} \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|.$$

§3. Locally convex topology generated by a fuzzy n -norm

In this section (X, N) is a fuzzy n -normed space, that is, X is real vector space and N is fuzzy n -norm on X . We form the family of n -seminorms $\|\bullet, \bullet, \dots, \bullet\|_\alpha$, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, according to Theorem 2.1. This family generates a family \mathcal{F} of seminorms

$$\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, \bullet\|_\alpha, \quad \text{where } x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X \text{ and } \alpha \in (0, 1).$$

The family \mathcal{F} generates a locally convex topology on X ; see [2, Def.(37.9)], that is, a basis of neighborhoods at the origin is given by

$$\{x \in X : p_i(x) \leq \epsilon_i \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n\},$$

where $p_i \in \mathcal{F}$ and $\epsilon_i > 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. We call this the locally convex topology generated by the fuzzy n -norm N .

Theorem 3.1 *The locally convex topology generated by a fuzzy n -norm is Hausdorff.*

Proof Given $x \in X$, $x \neq 0$, choose $x_1, \dots, x_{n-1} \in X$ such that x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x are linearly independent. By Theorem 2.1(A3) we find $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ such that $\|x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x\|_\alpha > 0$. The desired statement follows; see [2, Theorem (37.21)]. \square

Some topological notions can be expressed directly in terms of the fuzzy-norm N . For instance, we have the following result on convergence of sequences. We remark that the definition of convergence of sequences in a fuzzy n -normed space as given in [16, Definition 2.2] is meaningless.

Theorem 3.2 *Let $\{x_k\}$ be a sequence in X and $x \in X$. Then $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in the locally convex topology generated by N if and only if*

$$(3.1) \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} N(a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x, t) = 1$$

for all $a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} \in X$ and all $t > 0$.

Proof Suppose that $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in (X, N) . Then, for every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and all $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1} \in X$, there is K such that, for all $k \geq K$, $\|a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x\|_\alpha < \epsilon$. The latter implies

$$N(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x, \epsilon) \geq \alpha.$$

Since $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $\epsilon > 0$ are arbitrary we see that (3.1) holds. The converse is shown in a similar way. \square

In a similar way we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 3.3 *Let $\{x_k\}$ be a sequence in X . Then $\{x_k\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in the locally convex topology generated by N if and only if*

$$(3.2) \quad \lim_{k,m \rightarrow \infty} N(a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x_m, t) = 1$$

for all $a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} \in X$ and all $t > 0$.

It should be noted that the locally convex topology generated by a fuzzy n -norm is not metrizable, in general. Therefore, in many cases it will be necessary to consider nets $\{x_i\}$ in place of sequences. Of course, Theorems 3.2 and 3.3 generalize in an obvious way to nets.

§4. Fuzzy n -norms on finite dimensional spaces

In this section (X, N) is a fuzzy n -normed space and X has finite dimension at least n . Since the locally convex topology generated by N is Hausdorff by Theorem 3.1. Tihonov's theorem [2, Theorem (23.1)] implies that this locally convex topology is the only one on X . Therefore, all fuzzy n -norms on X are equivalent in the sense that they generate the same locally convex topology.

In the rest of this section we will give a direct proof of this fact (without using Tihonov's theorem). We will set $X = \mathbb{R}^d$ with $d \geq n$.

Lemma 4.1 *Every n -seminorm on $X = \mathbb{R}^d$ is continuous as a function on X^n with the euclidian topology.*

Proof For every $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, let $\{x_{j,k}\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ be a sequence in X converging to $x_j \in X$. Therefore, $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{j,k} - x_j\| = 0$, where $\|x\|$ denotes the euclidian norm of x . From property (S4) of an n -seminorm we get

$$\| \|x_{1,k}, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| - \|x_1, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| \| \leq \|x_{1,k} - x_1, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\|.$$

Expressing every vector in the standard basis of \mathbb{R}^d we see that there is a constant M such that

$$\|y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\| \leq M \|y_1\| \dots \|y_n\| \text{ for all } y_j \in X.$$

Therefore,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{1,k} - x_1, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| = 0$$

and so

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \| \|x_{1,k}, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| - \|x_1, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| \| = 0.$$

We continue this procedure until we reach

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{1,k}, x_{2,k}, \dots, x_{n,k}\| = \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|.$$

□

Lemma 4.2 *Let (\mathbb{R}^d, N) be a fuzzy n -normed space. Then $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha$ is an n -norm if $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is sufficiently close to 1.*

Proof We consider the compact set

$$S = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^{dn} : x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \text{ is an orthonormal system in } \mathbb{R}^d\}.$$

For each $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ consider the set

$$S_\alpha = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in S : \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha > 0\}.$$

By Lemma 4.1, S_α is an open subset of S . We now show that

$$(4.1) \quad S = \bigcup_{\alpha \in (0, 1)} S_\alpha.$$

If $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in S$ then (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) is linearly independent and therefore there is β such that $N(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, 1) < \beta < 1$. This implies that $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\beta \geq 1$ so (4.1) is proved. By compactness of S , we find $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m$ such that

$$S = \bigcup_{i=1}^m S_{\alpha_i}.$$

Let $\alpha = \max\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m\}$. Then $\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha > 0$ for every $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in S$.

Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$ be linearly independent. Construct an orthonormal system e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n from x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n by the Gram-Schmidt method. Then there is $c > 0$ such that

$$\|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|_\alpha = c \|e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\|_\alpha > 0.$$

This proves the lemma. □

Theorem 4.1 *Let N be a fuzzy n -norm on \mathbb{R}^d , and let $\{x_k\}$ be a sequence in \mathbb{R}^d and $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$.*

(a) *$\{x_k\}$ converges to x with respect to N if and only if $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in the euclidian topology.*

(b) *$\{x_k\}$ is a Cauchy sequence with respect to N if and only if $\{x_k\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in the euclidian metric.*

Proof (a) Suppose $\{x_k\}$ converges to x with respect to euclidian topology. Let $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1} \in X$. By Lemma 4.1, for every $\alpha \in (0, 1)$,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-1}, x_k - x\|_\alpha = 0.$$

By definition of convergence in (\mathbb{R}^d, N) , we get that $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in (\mathbb{R}^d, N) . Conversely, suppose that $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in (\mathbb{R}^d, N) . By Lemma 4.2, there is $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ such that $\|y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\|_\alpha$ is an n -norm. By definition, $\{x_k\}$ converges to x in the n -normed space $(\mathbb{R}^d, \|\cdot\|_\alpha)$. It is known from [8, Proposition 3.1] that this implies that $\{x_k\}$ converges to x with respect to euclidian topology.

(b) is proved in a similar way. □

Theorem 4.2 *A finite dimensional fuzzy n -normed space (X, N) is complete.*

Proof This follows directly from Theorem 3.4. □

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